

Supplementary data and figures

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Title: **Treatment of wood with atmospheric plasma discharge: Study of the treatment process, dynamic wettability and interactions with a waterborne coating**

Research part: *Results and discussion - Discharge intensity and plasma streamers distribution*

Figure S1: Enlarged photos of the samples, exposed to plasma discharges. Above each particular photo there are stated the normal density and moisture content of material.

Figure S2: Overall comparison of distribution (thin lines) and average (thick lines) of detected light intensity, measured in the discharges.

Table S1: Advancing and receding contact angle (CA) data, obtained with Wilhelmy plate method.

Type of wood	Treatment	Liquid	CA, advancing		CA, receding		
			Average	St. deviation	Average	St. deviation	
Spruce	Untreated	Water	46.3	5.3	15.9	12.0	
	Plasma treated		35.2	4.1	8.5	10.4	
	Untreated	Diiodomethane	19.5	3.2	0.0	0.0	
	Plasma treated		17.4	9.3	0.0	0.0	
	Untreated	Formamide	38.3	2.8	7.2	9.0	
	Plasma treated		34.0	4.3	13.5	8.8	
	Untreated	Coating	46.1	2.1	0.0	0.0	
	Plasma treated		37.8	4.2	0.0	0.0	
	Thermally modified spruce	Untreated	Water	64.2	1.9	15.6	13.1
		Plasma treated		58.8	2.8	23.0	11.9
Untreated		Diiodomethane	8.1	5.7	0.0	0.0	
Plasma treated			2.4	4.7	0.0	0.0	
Untreated		Formamide	42.4	1.7	18.7	10.0	
Plasma treated			41.2	0.5	24.3	5.3	
Untreated		Coating	23.9	13.2	0.0	0.0	
Plasma treated			21.3	11.3	0.0	0.0	
Beech		Untreated	Water	56.5	3.2	10.2	9.3
		Plasma treated		28.8	2.8	11.2	26.3
	Untreated	Diiodomethane	9.4	12.5	0.0	0.0	
	Plasma treated		5.8	6.7	0.0	0.0	
	Untreated	Formamide	25.3	7.2	0.0	0.0	
	Plasma treated		22.4	6.1	0.0	0.0	
	Untreated	Coating	47.7	4.3	0.0	0.0	
	Plasma treated		37.4	3.4	0.0	0.0	
	Thermally modified beech	Untreated	Water	77.4	3.5	7.1	7.1
		Plasma treated		54.8	3.7	13.3	6.6
Untreated		Diiodomethane	25.9	10.3	0.0	0.0	
Plasma treated			21.2	2.6	0.0	0.0	
Untreated		Formamide	31.6	2.8	2.9	5.3	
Plasma treated			28.6	4.5	1.0	3.1	
Untreated		Coating	28.3	3.9	0.0	0.0	
Plasma treated			23.8	3.1	0.0	0.0	

Figure S3 Examples of beech and spruce wood segmentations, including the percentage of non-air voxels. The scale bar represents 500 μm.